

THE NEW COVENANT IN PAUL

By

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The concept of covenant is central to the narrative plot structure of the Bible. Careful research and explanation of covenants in the storyline of the Bible help to see the progression of God's plan in history. In the Bible, God expressed his goodwill in entering a covenantal relationship with humankind.¹ God chose to establish his covenantal relationship with Adam, Noah, Abraham, Moses, and David, and with the new covenant community through Christ. When God chose people to fulfill his plans and purposes, he called them, promised blessings to them, and gave them stipulations. The covenant also functioned as an identity and boundary marker in relation to God and other people groups.² The conception of the covenant is significant in the Old Testament, intertestamental Judaism, and New Testament.³ The biblical authors relied on a covenantal framework while developing their theology of—God and his relationship with his people⁴—under the inspiration of the Holy Spirit.

There is much debate on whether the covenant was a dominant theme in Paul's theology.⁵ If the overarching story of the Bible has a significant conceptual framework of the covenant, how important it is for Paul to make use of such a framework? What does "covenant" mean to Paul? Is it a significant theme in his theology? How does he characterize the new

¹ Peter John Gentry and Stephen J Wellum, *Kingdom through Covenant: A Biblical-Theological Understanding of the Covenants* (Wheaton, Ill.: Crossway, 2012), 21.

² Ellen Juhl Christiansen, *The Covenant in Judaism and Paul: A Study of Ritual Boundaries As Identity Markers* (Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1995), 2.

³ Christiansen, *The Covenant*, 2.

⁴ Christiansen, *The Covenant*, 7-8.

⁵ Joshua Greever, "The New Covenant in Ephesians" (PhD Diss., The Southern Baptist Theological Seminary, 2014), 16.

covenant ministry in relation to the old covenant? How does he understand his role as a minister of the new covenant ministry of the Holy Spirit? Some of these questions guide a Bible student to explore and learn from Paul's theology and serve the church with the understanding of the new covenant ministry.

Thesis

In this paper, I argue that the new covenant is a significant conceptual framework in Paul's theology despite the limited usage of the word "covenant" (διαθήκη).⁶ Paul explained his theology of salvation (soteriology), morals (ethics), church (ecclesiology), and future (eschatology)⁷—as a minister of the new covenant—to the new covenant community. It is not to say that the new covenant is a "central" or "main" theme in his theology. Instead, the new covenant is an underlying conceptual framework⁸ and a crucial part of his Jewish worldview. Paul also maintained that the new covenant is distinct from the old covenant in its scope, nature, agency, community, glory, and end result. Paul carefully explained the characteristics of the new covenant, its relation with the old covenant promises and laws, and the role of the Holy Spirit in transforming believers into the image of Christ.

Methodology

In this paper, first, I provide different positions on the significance of the covenant in Paul and I argue that the covenant is significant in Paul's thought and the support it with the writings of Pauline scholars. Second, I provide a brief Pauline theology of covenant,

⁶ Joshua Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17. The basic structure and some aspects of the thesis were adopted from the PhD Dissertation of Joshua Greever. However, it was modified and further developed according to the requirements of current paper.

⁷ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17.

⁸ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17.

characteristics of the new covenant, and their relation to the old covenant by exegeting the chosen pericopes of the Pauline literature.⁹

Positions on the Significance of Covenant in Paul

There is much debate on whether the covenant was a dominant theme in Paul's theology. For example, James Dunn surveyed the usage of the word "covenant" (διαθήκη) in Paul's literature and concluded that the conception of covenant theology is insignificant in Paul's theology. On the other hand, Stanley Porter argued that a serious study of the semantic domain of the words associated with διαθήκη is helpful to understand the concept of covenant in Paul. He denied the conclusions based on a word study of one term "covenant" (διαθήκη).¹⁰

Covenant Concept is Ambivalent

James D. G. Dunn argues that Paul's conception of the covenant was ambivalent. Paul did not use the term "covenant" (διαθήκη) frequently in his writings. He did not write his theological reflections on the covenant. He only used the term "covenant" (διαθήκη) in order to respond to his opponents. Dunn brings an interesting argument to the table. He argues that Paul knew that the covenant is central to the Jewish theology expressed by God's election of Israel and his faithfulness. Despite his knowledge of the covenant, he did not employ it when he wrote his theology to the church. This questions the significance of covenant in Paul, whether it is a remnant product of his pre-conversion theology, or whether it is part of his new theology post-conversion to Christianity.¹¹

Dunn argues that Paul did not make use of the conception of the covenant as an apostle to the Gentiles. He employed the word διαθήκη when he corrected the misunderstanding of the heirs of

⁹ This paper is not aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of the covenant in Paul due to its limitation in size.

¹⁰ W.S. Campbell, "Covenant and New Covenant," in *Dictionary of Paul and His Letters*, The IVP Bible Dictionary Series, ed. Gerald F Hawthorne, Ralph P Martin, and Daniel G Reid (Downers Grove, Ill.: InterVarsity Press, 1993), 179-180. Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17.

¹¹ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17.

the promise. He underscored that Gentiles who put their faith in Christ are legitimate heirs to the covenant with the fathers. Paul conceived “covenant” only in relation to Israel. Christians are engrafted into the covenant community of Israel.¹² Dunn also argues that the unity of the church is of utmost importance to Paul, not necessarily theological disagreements of the covenant at the Eucharist.¹³

Covenant is a Subordinate Concept to the Concept of Promise

H. A. A. Kennedy considers that covenant is insignificant in Paul’s thought. He identified the close connection between the words “blessing” (εὐλογία) or “promise” (ἐπαγγελία), and “covenant” (διαθήκη). He argues that Paul interpreted the blessings and promises as to the covenant. The concept of promise is more significant than the concept of covenant. He argues that διαθήκη is the counterpart of ἐπαγγελία. In Ephesians 2:12, Paul calls the covenants the covenants of the promise.¹⁴

The contents of the covenants in the Old Testament were the promises that are fulfilled in Christ (Rom 4:13). He agrees that Paul used the covenant ideas of the terms προσαγωγή and παρρησία in Ephesians 2:18 and 3:12. However, he rejects the idea that Paul connected the death of Christ with the inauguration of the new covenant. In Kennedy’s view, the concept of the covenant for Paul is subordinate to the concept of promise.¹⁵

¹² Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 18.

¹³ Dunn, James D. G. *1 Corinthians*, New Testament Guides (Sheffield, England: Sheffield Academic Press, 1995), 76-79.

¹⁴ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 4-5.

¹⁵ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 4-5.

Covenant Concept is Significant

In the Pauline letters, the word covenant (διαθήκη) occurred eight times (Rom 9:4, 11:27, 1 Cor 11:25; 2 Cor 3:6, 14; Gal 3:15, 17; 4:24). Paul referred to two covenants in Galatians 4:24, he echoed the covenant of Eucharist in 1 Corinthians 11:25, he characterized the new covenant (καινῆ διαθήκη) in 2 Corinthians 3:6, and he referred to the old covenant (παλαιᾶ διαθήκη) in 2 Corinthians 3:14.¹⁶

Despite the debate on whether the covenant was a dominant theme in Paul's theology, it is possible to argue reasonably that Paul is a covenant theologian. The authors of the New Testament did not always explicitly explain certain themes like covenant in their writings, it is possible that they presumed it. The authors who were raised as Jews and Pharisees were certainly exposed to the theology of the covenant. It applies to Paul because he was raised as a Pharisee. Paul could have explicitly avoided the term "covenant" to avoid the possibility of misinterpretation.¹⁷

E. P. Sanders argues that Judaism in the Second Temple period is not legalistic, but it is "covenantal nomism." It is dominated by the conception of God's electing grace. The concept of covenant is foundational despite the lack of ample evidence for the word "covenant" (διαθήκη) itself. Sanders attributes "covenantal nomism" to Paul. He argues that Paul understood Christianity as a new covenant specifically for the people who believe in Christ. In that sense, there are significant correspondences between Judaism and Paul's theology.¹⁸ It prompted a

¹⁶ Campbell, *Covenant and New Covenant*, 179-182.

¹⁷ W.S. Campbell, *Covenant and New Covenant*, 179-182.

¹⁸ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 4-5. Mark A. Seifrid, "The New Perspective on Paul and Its Problems," *Themelios* 25, no. 2 (2000): 4-6. E. P. Sanders is a covenantal Nominist. His views were adopted on the significance of covenant in Paul's theology. Sanders illustrates the concept of "covenantal nomism"—a person is secured by God's electing grace through the covenant and the person requires to respond to the stipulations of the covenant. The author of this paper do not necessarily agree with the views of covenantal nominism. It is not the object of this paper to argue against covenantal nominism. E. P. Sanders, *Paul and Palestinian Judaism: A Comparison of Patterns of Religion* (Philadelphia: Fortress, 1977).

serious debate among contemporary scholars if Paul should be legitimately considered an adherent of “covenantal nomism.”¹⁹ Some contemporary scholars showed evidence against covenantal nomism.²⁰

N. T. Wright argues that Paul maintained a strong covenant theology. He connects every thought of Paul to the conception of the covenant. He characterizes righteousness as participation in the covenant community and justification as God’s declaration of membership in the covenant community. Covenant is the overarching principle that binds “justification” and being “in Christ.” Abrahamic covenant is the foundation for all other God’s saving work for his people. God chose Abraham and his family to bring salvation to humankind. God made a covenant with Abraham, and he fulfilled it completely in Jesus Christ.²¹ Wright argues that the implicit narratives and allusions to the large biblical themes help us to trace the significance of covenant theology in Paul’s thought.²²

In Paul’s theology, the role of covenant functions at two levels—at the levels of idea and conviction.²³ Kaylor argues that covenant is a conviction for Paul that acts as a continual presence and prevalent reality in Paul’s life, work, and thought.²⁴ One of the challenges in explaining the concept of covenant in Paul is the aspect of the continuity of God’s promises in the Old Testament. The concept of covenant suggests a continuity in divine purpose in history. It relies on the faithfulness of God (Romans 3:21-26). In Romans 9:21, Paul argues that the

¹⁹ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 4-5.

²⁰ Seifrid, *The New Perspective on Paul and Its Problems*, 4-6.

²¹ N.T. Wright, *Justification: God’s Plan and Paul’s vision* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity, 2009), 63, 100. Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 9-10.

²² N.T. Wright, *Justification*, 63, 100. Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 9-10.

²³ R. D. Kaylor, *Paul’s Covenant Community: Jew and Gentile in Romans* (Atlanta: John Knox Press, 1988), 8-11.

²⁴ Kaylor, 4-5. Campbell, *Covenant and New Covenant*, 179-182.

inheritance does not only belong to all who are the physical descendants of Abraham. They should share the faith of Abraham in order to be reckoned as children of Abraham. God has added Gentiles to the covenant community to the faithful remnant in Israel (Ephesians 2:11-22).²⁵

Biblical Exegesis of Selected Pericopes in Paul's Epistles

Galatians 3:15-25 (Law, Promise, and Covenant)

In this passage, Paul makes a case that those who rely on the faith are the children of Abraham. In the contemporary Jewish perspective, one should follow the law strictly to be counted as righteous before God. Paul's Jewish opponents demanded obedience to the law. They require that Gentiles should follow the law and customs of Jews to be justified by God. Paul rejects the notion of righteousness obtained by following the law (legalism).²⁶ The implication is that the new covenant does not necessarily rely on the external signs and works of the law. The new covenant members are justified by the grace of God in Christ Jesus and are partakers of the Abrahamic blessings.

Paul did not condemn the people who follow the law. He argues that one should not rely on the law for justification and right standing before God. The only ground for justification is faith in Jesus Christ. There are two premises in his argument in response to his opponents: First, justification is only by God's grace in Christ Jesus, obedience to the law is not a requirement. Second, Gentiles are not obligated to follow the law.²⁷

²⁵ Campbell, *Covenant and New Covenant*, 179-182.

²⁶ Douglas J. Moo, *Galatians*, Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2013), 224.

²⁷ Moo, *Galatians*, 224.

Paul’s opponents insisted that Gentiles should obey the righteous requirement of circumcision just like Abraham. God called Abraham and established his covenant with him. He also promised him that he will be a blessing to the nations. However, Abraham was circumcised as a sign of the covenant. He was also commanded to institute circumcision for his offspring as a sign of the covenant. Israelites were reiterated to adhere to circumcision in Moses’ law. Paul’s opponents concluded that if Abraham and his descendants followed circumcision, Gentiles should be circumcised and adhere to the law to be part of the covenant community. Paul deferred from his Jewish opponents in interpreting and applying Abrahamic covenant and Mosaic law. He argued that following the law and circumcision for justification is a radical break with faith in Christ.²⁸

Paul also answered the question of why God gave law if it did not fulfill the promise and did not benefit his people. In his answer, he also presented the purpose and result of the law and the promise. He argues based on two premises: First, the law and promise are distinct in their purposes. The law was given to expose the sin and exacerbate it. The law was never intended to bring life. Second, the law lasted and in function as a guardian till Christ came.²⁹ Christ gives life as people put their faith in Christ.

In this passage, Paul explained that God’s promise to Abraham only belongs to the one “seed” i.e., Jesus Christ. Those who are in Christ are legitimate heirs of the promise of the Abrahamic covenant. Paul related the word “promise” (ἐπαγγελία) with the word “covenant” (διαθήκη). The word “promise” (ἐπαγγελία) explains the idea of —God’s faithfulness in calling and blessing Abraham with the blessings of —land, descendants, and channel of blessing to other nations (Gen 12:1-3, 15:1-5, 17:1-8, and 22:15-18). It also covers the idea of God’s promise of

²⁸ Moo, *Galatians*, 224.

²⁹ Moo, *Galatians*, 225.

his faithfulness to the patriarchs (Gen 26:1-5, 28:13-15, 35:11-12). The idea of God's promise to fathers is prevalent in the New Testament (Acts 13:23,32; 26:6; Rom 4:13-20; 9:4-9; 15:8; Heb 6:12,15,17).³⁰ Similarly, the plural form of ἐπαγγελία captures the idea of God's provision of promises and reiteration of those promises.³¹

The promises were given to Abraham and his seed (τῷ Ἀβραάμ ... καὶ τῷ σπέρματι αὐτοῦ). Paul knew the semantic meaning of the word "seed" (σπέρμα) in Genesis 15:18 and 17:8 (LXX). He was fully aware that the word "seed" (σπέρμα) could be used as a collective form for the descendants. However, in some interpretations, the word "seed" (σπέρμα) is particularly used for the one "seed" i.e., Isaac. It is well attested by the usage of the word "seed" to refer to the seed of the woman and seed of the David etc., in the Hebrew scriptures. Paul applied this method of interpretation when he applied the word "seed" (σπέρμα) of the promise to one person Jesus Christ and the people who believe in him.³²

Romans 11:25-27 (New Covenant, Mystery of Israel's Salvation, and Inclusion of Gentiles)

In this passage, Paul reminds us that Jews will be engrafted into the olive tree (covenant community) if they embrace faith. Jews are not saved because of their rebellion in not having faith in Christ. However, there is still provision for Jews if they return to Christ. God is willing to graft them into the olive tree. God did not abandon Israel forever. It is a mistake to claim that Israel was altogether abandoned by God. The mystery (μυστήριον) of the eschatological salvation of Israel is hidden in the gospel of Jesus Christ. Mystery does not necessarily be a complex puzzle. Paul refers to the idea of God's plan being hidden before, and

³⁰ Moo, *Galatians*, 225-226.

³¹ Moo, *Galatians*, 228.

³² Moo, *Galatians*, 228.

revealed now through the gospel (Rom 16:25, 1 Cor 2:1, 7; 15:51, Eph 1:9; 3:3, 4, 9; 5:32; 6:19, Col 1:26-27; 1 Tim 3:9, 16).³³ Paul revealed God’s eternal plan to alleviate the pride of the Gentiles in judging Israel.³⁴

There is much debate on the word mystery (μυστήριον) and its implications for Israel and Gentiles. It relates to the period in which the salvation of all people is complete with the inclusion of remnant Israel in the end times. After “all Israel” is saved, the end arrives, and no further addition of Gentiles. Schreiner pointed out that the mystery is three-fold. First, there was a partial hardening for the people of Israel for a limited period of time. Second, Gentiles will be saved and added before the salvation of Israel. Third, all of Israel will be saved.³⁵

There is also disagreement on the meaning of the term “Israel” in this passage. Some suggested the term “Israel” refers to both Jews and Gentiles who believe in Jesus. In some places, Paul indicated that believers are true Jews and truly circumcised by faith (Rom 2:28-29, Phil 3:3), children of Abraham (Rom 4:1-17, Gal 3:6-9, 26-29), and the Israel of God (Gal 6:16). It is reasonable to argue that Paul referred to both Jews and Gentiles as “Israel.” However, this interpretation is not supported by the immediate context of Romans 9-11. The focal point of Paul’s argument in this context is the salvation of ethnic Israel. Gentiles were added to the olive tree when the “natural branches” (ethnic Israel) are removed. In verse 25, Paul mentioned the partial hardening of ethnic Israel. Schreiner argues that it is unlikely that Paul changed his meaning of the word “Israel” as ethnic in verse 25 to “all believers” in verse 26. Schreiner argues that the term “Israel” refers to “ethnic Israel.”³⁶

³³ Schreiner, Thomas R. *Romans*. Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Books, 1998), 11p. (Accessed April 16, 2022. ProQuest Ebook Central).

³⁴ Schreiner, *Romans*, 11q.

³⁵ Schreiner, *Romans*, 11q.

³⁶ Schreiner, *Romans*, 11q-11r.

Paul revealed the mystery—all Israel shall be saved (παῖς Ἰσραὴλ σωθήσεται). However, he did not mean that all ethnic Israel will be saved throughout history without exception. It undermines God’s judgment on rebellious Jews. Schreiner pointed out that Paul indicated a restoration of a large number of ethnic Israel in the end times.³⁷

1 Corinthians 11:17-34 (The Covenant through the Body and Blood of Jesus Christ)

The purpose of the covenant is God’s provision of salvation for sinful people. The heart of the covenant is atonement. It is an act of recapitulation of the covenantal concepts of Passover and the sacrifices of the Sinai Covenant.

Paul had received this tradition from others. However, he was dutiful to the tradition that he received. He explained the significance of the ordinance and exhorted the Corinthians to adhere to it faithfully. The sacrificial atonement of Christ is central to the idea of the covenant. Paul echoed the words of the institution given by the Lord. In this speech act, Jesus took the bread and said that it was broken for people. He also took the cup and said it is the cup of the new covenant. In the Old Testament, Israelites were in a covenant relationship with the Lord through the Passover sacrifice and sacrifices on the altar.

God promised Israelites that he will deliver them from the Egyptians, and he instituted Passover as a memorial. Jew eat unleavened bread to remember their departure from Egypt and God’s deliverance from slavery. The chief of the family would pray for the Passover meal and distributes the broken pieces of a common loaf. This is a reminder and a symbolic expression of their deliverance.³⁸ When Jesus ordained Holy Communion, he signified his bodily death as an

³⁷ Schreiner, *Romans*, 11s.

³⁸ Blomberg, Craig L. *1 Corinthians*. The NIV Application Commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1994), 85.

atoning sacrifice for the sake of people who put their trust in him. Therefore, the bread and cup represent his atoning sacrifice. This was given as a memorial.³⁹

The day of the Passover was a memorial for Israel. Israelites celebrated memorials to remember their deliverance from Egypt. The Passover lamb was killed in place of the firstborn sons of the Israelite household. The blood of the lamb was coated on the doorposts and lintels of the Israelite houses. Jesus applied the memorial aspect to his new covenant.⁴⁰

Jesus added his new interpretation to the Passover meal in light of his forthcoming sacrifice. He handed down this tradition to the Apostles.⁴¹ The meaning of the word “is” denotes “stands for” or “represents.” The bread here represents the body of Christ which is given for people. The explanation “which is for you” is an abbreviated form to signify that it was “broken” or “given” to the people. The term “for you” carries a meaning beyond eating. The term “for you” carries a vicarious meaning. This expression possibly invokes the idea of the suffering servant “bore the sin of many” (Is 53:12). In many texts, Paul used the preposition “for” to indicate the vicarious death of Christ (1 Cor 15:3, Rom 5:6,8; 2 Cor 5:14, Gal 3:13).⁴² Jesus Paul is reiterated the same covenantal aspect. He reminded the Corinthians of the finished atoning sacrifice of Christ.

After the Passover meal, Jews drink a cup of wine. At this point, they read the promise of redemption in Exodus 6:6.⁴³ The rationale for using the term “cup” instead of “wine” is to signify the cup of God’s wrath in the Old Testament (Is 51:17). Christ has suffered the wrath of

³⁹ Blomberg, 85.

⁴⁰ Gardner, Paul. *1 Corinthians*. Zondervan Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament, (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2018). 509-510.

⁴¹ Gardner, 509-510.

⁴² Gardner, 509-510.

⁴³ Blomberg, 85.

God on our behalf. As he drank the cup of the wrath of God, he brought peace to the people and inaugurated the new covenant (Jer 31:31-34).⁴⁴

2 Corinthians 3:7-18 (Characteristics and the Glory of the New Covenant Ministry and Fading of the Old Covenant Ministry)

In this passage, Paul shed light on the glory of the new covenant. He built his thesis on the foundation of the old covenant. He knew that his readers were exposed to the old covenant and its glory. Now, Paul saw himself as a minister of the New Covenant and felt the urgency of disclosing the superiority of the new covenant and its glory. In verses 7-11, he reflected on Exodus 34:29-35 and dealt with the aspect of the glory of the covenants and emphasized the greater glory of the new covenant. In verses 12-18, he commented on Exodus 34:33-35, he discussed the barrier of the veil between God and his people in the old covenant and the superiority of the new covenant in transforming people to experience God's glory.⁴⁵ Paul argued that the new covenant is superior, greater in glory, and effective in comparison to the old covenant based on these three premises. It is a common rhetorical method in arguing from lesser to greater. The ministry of the old covenant served by Moses was a lesser starting point for Paul's argument. He used it as a foundation to explain the greater point i.e., the glory of the new covenant.⁴⁶ Paul did not simply contrast his ministry with the ministry of the old covenant in general terms. Instead, he specifically addressed how the new covenant ministry is different in its

⁴⁴ Blomberg, 85.

⁴⁵ Guthrie, George H. *2 Corinthians*. Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker, 2015), 204.

⁴⁶ Guthrie, 205.

type.⁴⁷ His ministry is in the form of the new covenant, and it ministers to people through the proclamation of God's word under the authority of the Spirit.

Old Covenant Ministry. Paul considered the ministry of the old covenant as a ministry of death. The genitive form of the word (*thanatou*) could be either objective genitive or adjectival genitive. In the sense of objective genitive, it is a ministry that produces death. In the sense of adjectival genitive, it is a ministry that is related to or characterized by death. The law that was written on the stones was the purpose of death. Paul made a serious allegation in questioning the very purpose and result of the ministry of the law. This is a perplexing assertion for Jewish scholars. However, Paul's interpretation of Exodus and his theology of the old covenant were developed based on the context of Exodus. Anyone who crossed the boundaries of the mountain died (Ex 19:12). Capital punishment of death is mandated for violation of the law for a variety of transgressions (Ex 21:12, 14-17, 28-29; 22:2, 19; 31:14-15).⁴⁸

In Exodus 34:7, when the Lord passed before Moses, he declared that he will not cleanse the guilty, bringing the guilt of the fathers on the children and the children's children to the third and fourth generation. In Exodus 34:35, after the statement of Israelites seeing the glorified face of Moses, Exodus records the words of the lawgiver concerning the observance of the Sabbath. He declared that everyone who does work on Sabbath must die (Exodus 35:2).⁴⁹

In verse 9, the ministry of the Spirit is characterized by righteousness, it overflows with glory, on the other hand, the old covenant ministry is characterized by condemnation, which was merely attended by glory. The word "condemnation" means "a judicial verdict involves penalty." The adjectival form of the word refers to the idea that the old covenant ministry was

⁴⁷ Guthrie, 206.

⁴⁸ Guthrie, 206.

⁴⁹ Guthrie, 212-213.

characterized by death. Paul pointed out that though the ministry of the old covenant brought glory on the face of Moses, it brought condemnation to people who broke the law. Israelites experienced a wide variety of punishments for violating the law including death. Therefore, Paul concluded that it is the ministry of death. In the context of Exodus, the law of the old covenant brought death.⁵⁰

The work of the old covenant involves the writing of the covenant on the tablets. God engraved his law on the tablets, it is a physical representation of God's covenant with Israel through Moses. The tablets were called the tablets of the covenant. They were placed in the ark of the covenant (Ex 24:12, 25:16, 31:18; 32:15). Paul was reminded of the ministry of Moses when he came down from the mount of Sinai with the tablets of the testimony (Hebrew Text) in hand (Ex 34:29) which were engraved by God himself (Exodus 34:1). Paul juxtaposed his new ministry of the Spirit that is written on the hearts of the people with the ministry of Moses that was written on the tablets (2 Cor 3:3).⁵¹

Despite the limited scope of the old covenant, it was adorned with glory (*en doxe*). Israelites experienced God's glory when they left Egypt. The glory of God was revealed in the cloud that led Israelites in the wilderness and the pillar of fire at night (Ex 40:34-38). The glory of God was descended on the mountain. When Moses consecrated the tabernacle, the glory of God was descended on the tabernacle and the tent was filled with the glory of God.⁵²

In 2 Corinthians 3:7-11, Paul's main theme is glory. He uses the noun form of the word *doxa* eight times. He argues that there is a difference in the degree of glory between the old

⁵⁰ Guthrie, 212.

⁵¹ Guthrie, 207.

⁵² Guthrie, 207.

covenant and the new covenant. The people in the old covenant could not look at Moses when he reflected the glory on his face. In other words, they are not allowed to stare at his face.⁵³

There is much debate on the meaning of the word *katergew* in verses 7 and 11. It could mean “exhaust,” “make ineffective,” “invalidate,” “to use up,” and “released from the obligation.” Paul widely used the term to suggest the meaning of “canceled” or “made inoperative.” The glory on the face of Moses was “fading.”⁵⁴ Despite the strong evidence, some scholars disagree with the idea of cancellation. Garrett argues that the term did not mean “fade away.” He argues that it carries the meaning of “render powerless” or making “inoperative.” Paul used the word four times in this passage, he consistently maintained it means “to make inoperative.” According to this interpretation, the glory on the face of Moses was made inoperative. The glory was extinguished by the veil, and it occurred multiple times. He used the veil when he was in the presence of people, he removed it in the presence of God.⁵⁵

The superiority of the New Covenant Ministry. In verse 8, Paul moves to his basic argument, the superiority of the new covenant ministry. It is the work of the Spirit that makes the ministry of the new covenant greater than the old covenant ministry. This is a higher and greater ministry. The Spirit gives life. Paul juxtaposed the ministry of life with the ministry of death. Instead of bringing death to people, the Spirit is giving life to people.⁵⁶

There are different meanings for the word “glory” (*doxa*) in secular Greek. The word *doxa* means a sentiment, opinion, or thought. When it referred to a person, it means the reputation or fame of a person. It often means esteem or honor in the inscriptions and the papyri.

⁵³ Guthrie, 208.

⁵⁴ Guthrie, 211.

⁵⁵ Guthrie, 212.

⁵⁶ Guthrie, 212.

In 1 Corinthians 4:10, Paul contrasted words when comparing the Corinthians as “glorious” and his ministry as “dishonored.” In 2 Corinthians 6:8, he contrasted “dishonor” with “glory”. Paul’s usage of the word “glory” needs to be understood with the backdrop of the Greek-Roman world. The glory of a person, family, or culture had a high value in a Corinthian culture which was exposed to the Roman imperial cult.⁵⁷ In this sense, the new covenant ministry is glorious and honorable. Though Paul’s primary orientation in 2 Corinthians 3:17-18 is not of glory as reflected in Greco-Roman culture. He was aware that his opponents and the church members were pursuing glory. Guthrie argued that Paul offered his biblical reflection as an alternative worldview that offers glory to all people who are part of the new covenant. As he was demonstrating the glory of his new covenant ministry in light of his culture, he was also exposing the falsehood of his opponent's contrast.⁵⁸ The new covenant ministry is glorious because it is the ministry to bring life through the work of the Spirit and the proclamation of God’s word.

Conclusion

The new covenant is a significant conceptual framework in Paul’s theology despite the limited usage of the word “covenant” (διαθήκη).⁵⁹ Paul explained his theology of salvation (soteriology), morals (ethics), church (ecclesiology), and future (eschatology)⁶⁰—as a minister of the new covenant—to the new covenant community.

Paul also maintained that the new covenant is distinct from the old covenant in its scope, nature, agency, community, glory, and end result. First, Paul made a clear distinction

⁵⁷ Guthrie, 207.

⁵⁸ Guthrie, 208.

⁵⁹ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17.

⁶⁰ Greever, *The New Covenant in Ephesians*, 17.

between the old covenant and the new covenant in terms of its agency. He argued that the primary agent in the new covenant is the Spirit. He coined the previous ministry as the ministry of death. He distinguished the ministry of the Spirit from the previous ministry. Second, he made a clear distinction between the result of both ministries. One ministry results in death and the other brings life through the spirit. The ministry of the old covenant was associated with death and the ministry of the new covenant brings life.⁶¹ Third, he made a clear distinction between the covenants in terms of their continuity. One ministry is not being continued and therefore it is ineffective, the other one is being inaugurated and therefore it remains forever.⁶²

⁶¹ Guthrie, 206-207.

⁶² Guthrie, 204-205.

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